

IMAGEM USER MANUAL

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Abstract *ImageM is a graphical user interface (GUI) for interactive exploration, processing and analysis of multi-dimensional images. It is developed in Matlab.*

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1 Introduction

The variety of images generated by modern imaging devices continuously provide new challenges for their exploration, interpretation, and exploitation: dimensionality (2D, 3D, 3D+T), volumetry (up to several gigabytes), heterogeneity of the pixel information (intensity, colour, several channels, spectrum...).

Matlab is an efficient software solution for image processing, as it provides native support for multi-dimensional array, and a large number of image processing methods through dedicated toolboxes. However, it lacks many features for facilitating the interactive interpretation of image data, such as ergonomic image visualisation and management of image meta-data.

The ImageM application proposes a graphical user interface that facilitates the application of the image processing algorithms provided by Matlab. The general design was largely inspired by the popular ImageJ software (Schneider et al., 2012; Schindelin et al., 2015). An overview of the interface is presented on Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1: Overview of the ImageM Graphical User Interface with a 3D color image. Image Viewer, Color profile display, 3D Orthoslices.

Its most notable features are:

- Interactive visualization of **multi-dimensional images** (2D, 3D, 3D+T...)
- Quick access to many image processing operations via **user-friendly interface** (menus and dialogs)

1 Introduction

- Viewers take into account the **image types** (intensity, colour, binary, label, vector...), making it possible to automatically adapt the display or available image processing options
- **Spatial calibration** of images is stored along the different processing steps, providing analysis measurements in user units
- **Multi-variate images** can be explored using multi-variate statistical approaches (PCA, multivariate histograms...) and machine learning approaches
- Most operators result in a command line that can be easily re-used for writing more complex scripts

Chapter [2](#) provides details about installation and configuration of the application. The Image data model is described in chapter [3](#). The operations available from image viewer menus are detailed in chapter [4](#).

2 Installation and Configuration

2.1 Requirements

To install ImageM you need a version of Matlab, and the following Matlab toolboxes :

- the image processing toolbox
- the Statistics and Machine Learning toolbox, for some algorithms devoted to data mining

Other libraries are required (see Section 2.3), but are packaged into the auto-installable archive.

2.2 Installation

The application can be installed using different ways.

2.2.1 Using App Manager

The simplest way to install ImageM is by using the application manager provided by Matlab:

1. Within the “Home” toolbar, select the “Add-ons...” button. This will open a “add on explorer” dialog.
2. In the search area, type “ImageM”. This will provide several selections. The first one should be the right one!
3. Click on the “ImageM” selection. This opens the page of the application on the Mathworks site.
4. Click on the “Add” button (on the right)

2.2.2 From Mathworks FileExchange

It is also possible to explore the different application directly from Mathworks user contribution web page. The location of the ImageM application is <https://fr.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/45847-imagem>.

Once the page is identified, the installation is similar to what described previously.

2.2.3 From the sources

It is also possible to get the source of the project, and manually adds the necessary repository. Please note that the ImageM application depends on several other libraries, that have to be installed as well.

2.3 Sources and dependencies

The latest versions of the sources are available on the project page on GitHub¹.

In addition to the Image Processing and the Statistics and Machine Learning toolboxes, the ImageM requires the following (free) libraries:

- the Image class², shortly described in chapter 3
- the MatStats library³, for the management of data tables
- the GUI Layout Toolbox V2⁴, for the graphical user interface
- some functionalities also require the MatGeom toolbox⁵

Each library has to be downloaded, extracted, and the path(s) to the required directories need to be added to the Matlab “path”. In most cases, an installation script (usually called “setupLibrary”) is provided in the root directory of the library.

¹<https://github.com/mattools/ImageM>

²<https://github.com/mattools/matlab-image-class>

³<https://github.com/mattools/matStats>

⁴<https://fr.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/47982-gui-layout-toolbox>

⁵<https://github.com/mattools/matGeom>

3 Image data

This chapter recalls the conventions for manipulating images within the ImageM application. The data model for images is managed by a class “Image”, described on its own project page¹.

3.1 Image dimensions

ImageM considers images as multi-dimensional arrays up to five dimensions. Images can have two or three spatial dimensions (denoted by XYZ), and one time dimension (T). Additionally, images can be composed of different channels. Channels may correspond to the red, green and blue channels of a RGB image, to fluorescence channels, or to the wavelengths of a multi-spectral image. This “channel” dimension is denoted by C.

3.2 Image types

In order to facilitate the interpretation of the data stored within images, different image types are considered:

grayscale images correspond to images containing scalar values stored as integers (usually uint8 or uint16).

intensity images correspond to images containing scalar values stored as floating point data types. The values may be negative and have various ranges.

binary images correspond to images containing boolean values, that can have only the values true or false.

label images (sometimes called label maps) correspond to images containing integer values, where the value correspond to the index of the label the pixel belong to. By convention, the value 0 correspond to the background. Note that binary images are sometimes considered as a special case of label images.

color images correspond to images containing three channels, one for each of the red, green and blue colors.

vector images correspond to images in which each pixel or voxel contains a list of values. Color images are a special case of vector images.

¹<https://github.com/mattools/matlab-image-class>

3.3 Image calibration

3.3.1 Image indexing

Elements of an image are indexed in the x, y order or in the (x, y, z) order. Indexing is 1-based, following Matlab convention for arrays (Fig. 3.1).

Figure 3.1: Coordinate system for representing uncalibrated images. First index corresponds to the x direction. Indices start at 1.

An element of an image is usually associated to a square region centered on its coordinates. Its bounds are therefore ± 0.5 around each dimension.

3.3.2 Spatial calibration

The spatial calibration of the image can be used to relate index coordinates to physical space coordinates. The Image class stores the spacing between elements (as a $1 \times d$ row vector, where d is the number of spatial dimensions), the coordinates of the first element (as a $1 \times d$ row vector), and the name of the calibration unit. These information can be used to provide results of image analysis operations in calibrated units (see Section 4.7).

3.3.3 Time calibration

For time-lapse images, the time origin, the time step between frames, and the time unit are also stored in the Image class.

3.4 Other meta-data

The image class also stores general-use meta data.

Name the name of the image, used to display frame titles.

FilePath the path to the file was loaded from.

ChannelNames the name of the channels. Can be used to identify channel from their names, or store channel-related information.

4 Image Frame menu

This chapter describes the menu operations available from the Image viewer frame. Note that depending on image dimensionality and type, some operators may be disabled.

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4.1 File Menu

Items in this menu allow to import/export images from/to various sources, or to interact with Matlab Workspace.

4.1.1 Importing and creating data

The following menu entries allow to create or import images from various sources.

New Image...

Creates a new image by specifying the dimensions and the type.

Open...

Opens an image and creates a new window to display it. Supports all image file formats provided by Matlab Image Processing, as well as more specific formats such as the MetaImage file format. 3D Tiff files as saved by ImageJ can also be imported.

Import ▸ Import from binary file

Imports an image from a raw data file, by specifying image size, data type and encoding.

Import ▸ Import series

Imports a multi-dimensional image from a series of 2D images. Specify the file name pattern and the indices of the files to import.

Import ▸ Import from workspace

Imports an instance of the image class, or a numeric array, from Matlab workspace into the interface.

Open Demo...

Opens one of the demo images bundled with the ImageM application. Demo images comprises classical Matlab images, as well as sample images from previous studies.

Open Table

Opens a text file as Table, and displays it in a new Table Frame.

4.1.2 Exporting and saving images

Save As...

Saves the current image into a file.

Export to Workspace

Exports the current image as a variable in Matlab Workspace.

4.1.3 Other commands

Close

Closes the current frame.

Quit

Close all frames and quit the application.

4.2 Edit Menu

Provides functions for managing the selection, and global settings.

Save Selection...

Save current selection as a text file.

Crop Selection

Create a new image based on the area enclosed by the current selection.

Print Image List

Display the list of image document currently open.

Settings

A sub-menu for choosing the value of several global options.

4.3 Image Menu

Provides operators to display information about image, and to perform basic image conversion utilities.

4.3.1 General information

Print Info

Displays general information about the current image.

Rename

Changes the name of the current image.

Duplicate

Creates a copy of the current image, keeping the same settings.

4.3.2 Calibration and conversion

Calibration

Several options to update spatial calibration of image, or to update channel names.

Set Image Type

Changes the type of the image, allowing to convert to label, grayscale, binary...

Convert Data Type

Changes the type of the underlying data array. Can choose a typical matlab numeric type (uint8, single...)

4.3.2.1 Image Type conversions

Several conversion utilities, to convert between 3D and vector images, or to “unfold” a multi-channel image into a table.

3D Image to Vector Image

Converts a 3D image into a vector image, by assimilating the z -axis to the channel axis.

Vector Image to 3D Image

Converts a vector image into a 3D image, by assimilating the channel axis to the z -axis.

Vector Image to RGB

Converts a vector image into a RGB color image, by specifying the channels indices to use for each of the red, green and blue channels of the result image.

Intensity Image to RGB

Converts a grayscale or intensity image into a color image by choosing the colormap and the value range.

Unfold Vector Image to Table

Converts a vector image into a data table, where each row corresponds to a pixel (or voxel), and each column corresponds to a channel (see Fig. 4.1). The resulting table can be used for data mining or classification tasks. The coordinates of the original pixels may be optionnally generated. The conversion from table to image is managed by the “Fold Table To Image” command (see section 5.2).

Unfold Vector Image Within Mask to Table...

Converts a specific region of a vector image into a data table, where each row corresponds to a pixel (or voxel), and each column corresponds to a channel.

Figure 4.1: Unfolding a color image into a data table. The resulting table has three columns, one for each of the three color channels.

4.3.2.2 Color and channels management

Utilities for color management (split / merge channels, extract a specific channel, re-order channels...).

Split RGB

Creates three new images from a color image, one for each of the red, green and blue channels.

Split Channels

Creates new images from a vector image, one for each channel of the original image.

Merge Channels...

Create a new RGB image by choosing the grayscale images for each of the red, green and blue channels.

Re-order Channels...

Choose a new order for the channels of a vector image.

4.3.3 Image shape transform

This section provides several elementary geometric transformations.

Figure 4.2: Geometric transforms applied on a color image. (a) Original image, (b) permutation of the x and y dimensions, (c) flip in the horizontal direction, (d) “left” (counter-clockwise) rotation.

Reshape

Changes the dimensions of the image, keeping the same number of total elements.

Permute Dimensions

Permute the dimensions of the image.

Horizontal Flip

Flips the image in the horizontal direction.

Vertical Flip

Flips the image in the vertical direction.

Rotate Right

Rotates the image clockwise.

Rotate Left

Rotates the image in counter-clockwise direction.

4.3.4 Other shape utilities

Orthogonal Projection

Projects the values of a 3D image into a plane along one of the main directions.

Extract Slice

Extracts a specific slice from a 3D image.

Extract Time Frame

Extracts a specific frame from a time-lapse image.

Invert Image

Inverts a grayscale image.

4.4 View Menu

Items in this menu allow to get informations on images, and to perform basic editing.

Set Display Range

Set the values corresponding to the minimal and maximal displayed values.

Set Color Map

Choose the color map for displaying intensity images, or label images.

Set Background Color

Set the background color, that is used for display of NaN values in intensity images.

4.4.1 Zoom

The current zoom level can be updated from menu items (note: these features are not available from the octave version).

Zoom In

Multiplies the current zoom level by 2.

Zoom Out

Divides the current zoom level by 2.

4 Image Frame menu

Zoom 1:1

Set the zoom level such that one displayed pixel corresponds to one image pixel.

Zoom Best

Adapts the current zoom level such that the entire image fits within the window.

Others

Provides several options to choose pre-determined zoom levels.

4.4.2 3D Views

Some utilities are provided for the visualization of 3D images

Show 3D OrthoSlices...

Opens a new window and displays three mutually orthogonal slices (see Figure 4.3-b).

Show 3D Isosurface...

Generates a 3D isosurface from an intensity image and a threshold level, and displays it in a new window (see Figure 4.3-c). Can be slow on large images.

Figure 4.3: Several representations of a 3D label image. (a) Result of 3D orthogonal representation. (b) Result of 3D isosurface computation. Original image from [Moukhtar et al. \(2019\)](#).

4.5 Process Menu

Comprises most of the image processing operators.

4.5.1 Intensity processing

Adjust Dynamic

Converts an intensity image into a 8-bits grayscale images by choosing the min and max intensities.

Replace Values

Replaces intensity or label values within an image. May be useful to remove or merge labels.

4.5.2 Image filtering

Provides several operators for removing noise or enhancing features from images. Most operators can be applied on 2D/3D images, and provide a preview of the result.

Box Mean filter...

Applies box filter on the current image (see Fig. 4.4-a). Filter is defined by the size of the box along each dimension.

Median Filter...

Applies median filter on the current image, by computing the median value in the neighborhood of each pixel (see Fig. 4.4-c). Filter is defined by the size of the neighborhood along each dimension.

Figure 4.4: Comparison of several noise removal filters. Median filters tends to better preserve edges than box or gaussian filters.

Gaussian Filter...

Applies Gaussian filter on the current image (see Fig. 4.4-b). Filter is defined by the sigma value of the gaussian kernel along each dimension. The size of the neighborhood is automatically computed from the sigma value.

Morphological Filters...

Morphological filtering of the current image. Parameters can be tuned from dialog (Fig. 4.5):

- the type of the morphological filter: dilation, erosion, closing, opening, (morphological) gradient, (morphological) laplacian, white top-hat, black top-hat
- the shape of the structuring element (square, disk...)
- the size of the structuring element

Figure 4.5: Interactive morphological filtering of a grayscale image.

Gradient

Computes the (Sobel) gradient of the grayscale or intensity image. The result is a vector image, each component corresponding to the gradient in one of the dimensions (see Fig. 4.6-b and -c).

Gradient Norm

Computes the norm of the gradient of the grayscale or intensity image. The result is an intensity image (see Fig. 4.6-a).

Norm

Computes the norm of a multi-channel image, as an intensity image.

Figure 4.6: Gradients computed on an intensity image. (a) Norm of the gradient. (b) Gradient along the x direction. (c) Gradient along the y direction.

4.5.3 Connectivity based operators

Several operators are based on the notion of connectivity, and provide powerful operations such as the selection of connected based on regional minima or maxima. The morphological reconstruction operator is also at the basis of kill borders or fill hoels operations.

Morphological Reconstruction...

Performs morphological reconstruction of a marker image constrained by a mask image. Can be performed on binary or grayscale images with the same size.

Kill Borders

Removes the regions that touch the borders of the image (see Fig. 4.7-b). Can be applied to a grayscale, binary, or label image.

Fill Holes

Removes holes within binary or intensity image (see Fig. 4.7-c).

Figure 4.7: Example of two operators based on connectivity. (a) Original image. (b) Result of Fill Holes operator. (c) Result of Kill Borders operator. Image from [Le et al. \(2019\)](#).

Regional Minima / Maxima

Extracts the regional minima or maxima from a grayscale or intensity image.

Extended Minima / Maxima

Extracts the extended minima or maxima from a grayscale or intensity image. The dialog allows to specify the dynamic of the minima/maxima as well as the connectivity.

Impose Minima

Imposes minima on a grayscale / intensity image. Often used to impose the markers of a watershed segmentation (see Section 4.5.4).

4.5.4 Image segmentation

Several operators for image segmentation. Results are usually returned as binary or label images.

Manual Threshold

Binarizes an image by manually choosing the threshold level (see Fig. 4.8).

Figure 4.8: Interactive segmentation of a grayscale image using manual segmentation. Image from *Le et al. (2019)*.

Auto Threshold...

Binarizes an image by using an automated threshold method. Method can be either Otsu, or minimum entropy.

Watershed...

Identifies catchment basins within a grayscale or intensity image using a watershed algorithm (*Vincent & Soille, 1991; Soille, 2003*). Some pre-processing may be needed. The result is a label image, each label corresponding to a basin of the original image.

K-Means Segmentation

K-means is a method for cluster analysis. It consists in building a partition of n observations into k clusters in which each observation belongs to the cluster with the nearest mean, serving as a prototype of the cluster. In the case of a grayscale image, this results in a multi-level threshold based on image intensities. In the case of a multi-variate image, each observation corresponds to an image element, and each component corresponds to a feature. The resulting clusters correspond to groups of pixels with similar or near colors or channel intensities.

Figure 4.9: Result of the *kmeans* method applied to a color image. (a) The colors correspond to the class index. (b) The colors correspond to the average color within the corresponding class.

Extended Min Watershed...

Concatenates several operations into a single operator. This operator consists in (1) computing extended minima, (2) imposing minima on the original image, and (3) applying the watershed algorithm. These three operations are integrated into a simple dialog that allows to choose the dynamic of the minima and the connectivity, and visualize a preview of the output (Figure 4.10). The result is a label image.

4.5.5 Binary / Label images processing

Some operators are more specific to binary images. Some of them may also be applied to label images.

Connected Components Labeling

Converts a binary image into a label image by identifying the connected components.

Area Opening

Removes the binary regions whose size (in number of pixels or voxels) is smaller than the specified threshold.

Figure 4.10: Interactive segmentation of a 3D grayscale image using watershed. Image from [Moukhtar et al. \(2019\)](#).

Keep Largest Region

Keeps the largest binary region within the image.

Distance Map

Computes the distance map of a binary image. For each foreground pixel or voxel, computed the distance to the nearest background pixel or voxel (see Fig. 4.11-a).

Geodesic Distance Map

Computes the geodesic distance map from a binary marker within a binary mask (see Fig. 4.11-b).

Figure 4.11: Several operators for binary images. (a) Distance map. (b) geodesic distance map within a binary mask (the marker is shown as a red cross). (c) Skeleton (shown as red overlay).

Skeleton

Computes the skeleton of each binary region (see Fig. 4.11-c).

Boolean Op...

Combines two binary images using logical operators (AND, OR, XOR...)

Binary Overlay

Creates a Color image by computing a binary overlay over a grayscale or color image.

Label To RGB...

Converts an label image into a RGB image by choosing LUT and background color.

Create Label Values Map...

Creates an intensity image by combining a label image, and a table containing a value associated to each label.

4.6 Tools

Selection of interactive tools, such as ROI selection or interactive measurements.

4.6.1 Selection of regions of interest

Select Rectangle

Selects a rectangular region of interest.

Select Points

Selects a region of interest composed of several points.

Select Polyline

Selects a polyline region of interest based on several vertices. Can be used to draw line profiles.

Select Polygon

Selects a polygon region of interest based on several vertices. Can be used to measure average values within regions.

Select Line Segment

Selects line segment based on two extremity points. Can be used to draw line profiles.

4.6.2 Drawing tools

Set Pixel to White

Changes the value of the selected pixel to white.

Brush

Draws onto the current image, using current value.

Flood Fill

Fills a connected region with the current value.

Pick Current Value/Color

Changes the current value / color from the picked pixel.

4.6.3 Interactive exploration tools

Some tools allow to interactively explore the values or the profiles within multi-dimensional images.

Print Current Point

Prints the value of selected pixel(s) on the command line.

Plot Image 3D Z-Profile

Opens a new plot window, and when clicking on a position of a 3D image slice, plots the corresponding z-profile.

Plot Vector Image Channels

Opens a new plot window, and when clicking on a position of a multi-channel image, plots the corresponding channel profile.

4.7 Analysis

Extracts quantitative information from images.

4.7.1 Interactive measurements

Set Image Scale

Sets the image spatial calibration from the current line segment selection.

Measure Points

Creates a new table containing the image values measured for each point in the current multi-point selection.

Measure Within Selection

Creates a new table containing the average image value measured within the current polygon selection.

Line Profile

Plots a lines profile of intensities (or three line profiles of color intensities) along a path previously defined by a “line selection” tool.

4.7.2 Image value distributions

Histogram

Computes the histogram of the values (or of the colors) within the image.

Figure 4.12: Computation of Histogram and Line profile of a color image.

Joint Histogram

Computes the joint histogram of two images with the same size. The result is a 2D image, where each axis corresponds to the intensities of one of the images, and the values correspond to the count of pixels or voxels that share the specified pair of values.

4.7.3 Analysis of Regions

Analys morphology and values of regions. Requires label (or binary) images.

Analyze Regions...

Opens a dialog to choose a selection of morphometric features. The result is a new data table with as many rows as the number of regions within the current label image.

Average Value by Region

Opens a dialog to choose a label image and an intensity image with same dimensions. The result is a new data table that contains for each region the average value of the corresponding pixels/voxels in the intensity image.

5 Table Management

Several image operators return results as data tables. Data tables are based on a $n \times p$ array, where n is the number of rows, usually corresponding to observations, and p is the number of columns, usually corresponding to features.

Data tables are displayed in their own frames, and a collection of operators for Tables is available from Table frame menu.

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5.1 File Menu

Commands within the File menu allow to load and save tables.

Open Table...

Opens a file stored in a text file such as a CSV (Coma-Separated-Values) file.

Save As...

Saves the table in the current frame as a CSV file.

Close

Closes the current frame.

Quit

Close all frames and quit the application.

5.2 Edit Menu

Commands within the Edit menu allow to combine tables and apply common edition operations on tables.

Rename

Changes the name of the current table.

Transpose

Transposes the current table, by interverting columns and rows.

Concatenate...

Concatenate two tables, either horizontally or vertically.

Select Rows...

Extracts a portion of the current table by manually selecting rows.

Select Columns...

Extracts a portion of the current table by manually selecting columns.

Filter From Column Values...

Extracts a portion of the current table by using a condition on the values within one of the columns.

Fold Table To Image...

Converts a table into an image, by “folding” the values into a 2D or 3D array. This is the counterpart of the “Unfold Vector Image To Table” operator (see section [4.3.2.1](#)).

5.3 Plot Menu

Plotting facilities are available from the Plot menu.

5.3.1 Distribution plots

Several commands allow to represents graphically the distribution of the values within a column.

Figure 5.1: Distribution plots of features within a table. (a) Histogram. (b) Box Plot. (c) Violin Plot.

Histogram...

Displays the histogram of values within one of the columns of the table (see Fig. 5.1-a).

Box Plot...

Displays the value distribution within one of the columns of the table as a box plot (see Fig. 5.1-b).

Box Plot by Group...

Displays the value distribution within one of the columns of the table as a box plot, by grouping the values according to the specified factor column.

Violin Plot...

Displays the value distribution within one of the columns of the table as a violin plot, by grouping the values according to the specified factor column (see Fig. 5.1-c).

5.3.2 Correlation plots

Another series of commands is better suited to represent correlations, or relationships between the values within two or more columns.

Scatter Plot...

Displays the observations as markers according to the coordinates in two columns.

Scatter Groups...

Displays the observations as markers according to the coordinates in two columns, using a color that depends on a factor column.

Figure 5.2: Correlation plots. (a) Result of “Pair Plot” on a subset of the iris data set. (b) Result of “Correlation Circles” on a subset of the cars data set.

Pair Plot

Pairwise scatter plots and histograms of table columns (See Fig. 5.2-a).

Correlation Circles

Represents the correlation matrix of table columns using colored circles (See Fig. 5.2-b). The intensity of the correlation is given by the size of the circle, while the color indicates whether the correlation is positive or negative.

5.3.3 Simple plots

Plot Columns

Display the values within the columns as curves, using row index as x-position.

Plot Rows

Display the values within the rows as curves, using column index as x-position.

5.4 Process Menu

Commands in this menu allow more elaborate processing of the underlying data table.

5.4.1 Dimensionality reduction

Principal Component Analysis

Performs a principal component analysis (PCA) of the current data table. A new frame opens, allowing to choose the results to display (score plots, loadings plot, scree plot...)

Non-Negative Matrix Factorization

Performs a non-negative matrix factorization (NMF) of the current data table. The user inputs the number of components, and two new tables are created, that correspond to the weights and the coefficients of the factorization.

5.4.2 Clustering

K-Means

Performs a k-means clustering of the data within the current table. User can choose the number of classes, and the result is provided as a new table containing the class index associated to each observation (row).

5.5 Help Menu

Print History

A simple utility that displays the commands registered within ImageM history.

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